

The Role of Quantum Mechanics at Neuronal Level on Creating Consciousness

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Abstract

The exploration of quantum consciousness and its implications on brain function has yielded profound insights into the complex interplay between quantum physics and neuroscience. In recent years, quantum effects have been identified in critical biological processes, including vision through photoreceptors, olfaction via quantum tunnelling, and avian navigation through quantum entanglement. Neuronal avalanches, characterized by their variable sizes, have been revealed as a fundamental aspect of brain activity, operating at different critical states. Quantum fluctuations, operating at an ultramicroscopic scale, have been proposed to play a pivotal role in tipping the balance between these critical states, thereby altering the state of consciousness. This delicate equilibrium between quantum chaos and stability suggests that quantum dynamics could orchestrate significant changes in the synchronization of neuronal firing patterns, consequently impacting cognitive functions, behaviour, and the state of consciousness itself. This review navigates the intricate terrain of quantum consciousness, offering a comprehensive overview of its relevance to biology, cognitive processes, and the broader understanding of consciousness itself.

Keywords: Quantum Physics, Neuroscience, Consciousness, Biological Processes, Brain Activity, Cognitive Functions

Introduction

Quantum consciousness, initially introduced by Nobel Prize-winning physicist Roger Penrose and Stuart Hameroff in 1996 (Hameroff & Penrose 1996), has emerged as a captivating theory known as "orchestrated objective reduction" or Orch OR theory. This theory postulates that the initiation of quantum dynamics occurs within cellular structures, specifically microtubules, ultimately leading to alterations in neuronal function. These alterations are believed to significantly impact cognitive output within interconnected

neuronal networks (Hameroff 2012). This groundbreaking theory aligned with the notion of the non-linear functioning of the entire nervous system, a concept subsequently supported by several research groups (Tognoli & Kelso 2014, Wolf et al. 2014). The non-linearity inherent in neuronal connections is posited to enhance the influence of quantum mechanics on the brain's computational capacity, thus optimizing the encoding of information through the amplification of quantum events at nanoscales (Harish & Hansel 2015).

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However, the Orch OR theory faced challenges related to the self-averaging nature of quantum fluctuations. The self-averaging phenomenon reduces the significance of minute quantum particles within the complex cellular environment, casting doubt on the substantial impact of quantum mechanics as a component of the brain's super-dynamic processes (Koch & Hepp 2006). Subsequent experiments, nevertheless, shed light on the multifaceted roles played by quantum mechanics in various biological events, including photosynthesis (Loewenstein 2013), olfaction (Huelga & Plenio 2013), sleep (Strongman, L 2014), and general anaesthesia (Emerson et al. 2013). It became apparent that quantum mechanics could exert its influence on neuronal firing and, consequently, consciousness at the ultramicroscopic level. For example, it could affect the spin of electrons and establish quantum entanglement between phosphorus nuclei. Given that the fundamental constituents of every cell are atoms, the applicability of the atomic structure principles of quantum physics, as elucidated by Bohr (Owen & Guta 2019), to cellular processes is now a plausible consideration. In this discussion, we explore the most recent theories regarding the impact of quantum events on neuronal activities associated with consciousness.

History of Consciousness Studies

The exploration of consciousness has presented a challenge throughout history. In the 17th century, René Descartes proposed a scientific approach to understanding individual awareness of thoughts, memories, sensations, and environments, collectively referred to as consciousness (Owen & Guta 2019). Descartes delineated the body into two components: matter responsible for movement and the immaterial mind, which engenders thoughts. This perspective, however, encountered opposition from scientists who regarded the mind as an emergent property of matter, specifically the brain. Gustav Fechner was among these scientists, advocating that body and mind represent two facets of a unified

being (Fechner 1860). Nevertheless, the question of how mind arises from matter remained unresolved.

Advancements in human physiology enhanced our comprehension of the nervous system and its cognitive functions. A particularly intricate facet of cognitive function pertained to personal and environmental awareness, captivating the attention of numerous scientists. Considering that the brain consists of atoms, like other physical matter, it appeared logical to speculate that it adhered to the same fundamental principles governing the physics of matter (Bohr 1934). This notion subsequently gave rise to the hypothesis that quantum physics might hold the key to elucidating various aspects of brain function, including behaviour and consciousness.

Quantum Dynamics in Biology

Quantum dynamics in living systems has found multifaceted applications across various biological phenomena. Photoreceptors, pivotal in the visual process, rely on intracellular rhodopsin protein to perform their essential role in vision. Loewenstein's research unveiled a discernible level of quantum fluctuation in rhodopsin when exposed to light (Loewenstein 2013, Wang et al. 2016). Another compelling instance is the involvement of quantum tunnelling in facilitating electron transfer across olfactory receptors (Huelga & Plenio 2013). In avian species, quantum entanglement, an outcome of protein-protein interactions, plays a pivotal role in avian magnetic compass navigation, enabling birds to perceive electromagnetic waves (Hiscock et al. 2016).

Recent Advances in Understanding Consciousness

A compelling avenue of exploration in understanding consciousness lies in the examination of mechanisms underlying unconsciousness.

Studying Consciousness through the Lens of Unconsciousness

The concept of cognitive unconsciousness was initially introduced by John Kihlstrom (Kihlstrom 1987) as a means of assessing the impact of stimuli on behaviour, even if these stimuli remain beyond the subject's conscious awareness. An illustrative example pertains to individuals with extensive lesions in the occipital cortex (visual cortex) who could recognize visual stimulus characteristics despite their inability to perceive them visually (Weiskrantz et al. 1974).

Altered states of consciousness can also be achieved through general anaesthesia. During anaesthesia, an individual transitions away from self and environmental awareness into various states of unconsciousness. It has been proposed that anaesthetic agents, by accelerating the movement of electrons within protein chains (Hameroff 2018), may significantly affect electron flow due to their affinity for various cellular proteins. Subsequent observations of fluctuations in the magnetic properties of protein particles at the quantum level, referred to as the quantum speed of electrons, using electron spin resonance, corroborated this suggestion (Hameroff 2018, Rinaldi 2014). These instances, among others, have fuelled the idea of potential involvement of quantum-level substances in consciousness. The transmission of such substances between neurons is believed to play a pivotal role in the creation of consciousness, while their absence hinders such processes.

Consciousness Transmission: Exploring Potential Mediators

To substantiate the physical transmission of consciousness along neuronal networks, identifying the substances capable of such transmission remains a central concern. These candidate substances must possess the ability to traverse neurons at a quantum level, specifically within ultramicroscopic synaptic spines. One proposition for a "quantum-level mediator" is a group of molecules known as psychons (Li et al. 2019). Psychons are

theorized to share analogous characteristics with neurotransmitters. Much like neurotransmitters, which perform specific roles individually, each psychon is thought to transmit a distinct facet of the conscious experience. These quantum substances are believed to continuously flow between the dendritic branches of neurons, primarily within the cerebral cortex, referred to as dendrons (Beck & Eccles 1992).

Psychons are postulated to enhance the likelihood of neuronal firing within specific networks through mechanisms such as quantum tunnelling, a phenomenon that increases neuronal membrane permeability via transmembrane ionic channels. Holden et al. demonstrated that conventional neurotransmitters, including serotonin, exhibit a notable degree of tunnelling characteristics akin to psychons, influencing the voltage sensitivity of channels and, consequently, their permeability to ions through electron tunnelling (Adams & Petruccione 2020). Collectively, this quantum mechanical electron tunnelling (QBET), facilitates the selective passage of quantum particles through the otherwise impermeable phospholipid cell membrane.

Another group of proposed mediators operating at the quantum level involves Posner molecules (Fisher 2015). These molecules are believed to modulate neuronal firing, thereby impacting cognitive behaviour and consciousness. Posner molecules rely on cellular energy and release it by breaking down cellular energy storage, known as adenosine triphosphate (ATP), resulting in elevated cellular phosphates. Fisher's hypothesis posits that phosphorus in Posner molecules, with an altered spin state, binds to calcium ions with a zero-spin state, leading to intracellular translocation of Posners. This enlargement of Posner molecules subsequently triggers heightened neuronal activation, thereby influencing cognitive processes (Fisher 2015). A similar alteration in phosphorus spin within

nuclei, induced by various isotopes of xenon (anaesthetic agents), was also documented by Li et al. (Li et al. 2019), resulting in varying levels of unconsciousness.

The Utility of Quantum Consciousness

Exploring the physics of quantum particles within neurons can lead us down two distinct paths: one characterized by a chaotic interplay of unstable particles in the warm and moist environment of the brain on a macroscopic scale, and the other marked by a precisely orchestrated amplification of electrical neuron firing on a microscale (Satinover 2001). Neurons are known to generate intricate patterns of collective activity referred to as "neuronal avalanches" (Beggs & Plenz 2004). These avalanches exhibit varying sizes, with smaller groups occurring more frequently than larger ones. This variability allows the brain to maintain an optimal state of readiness for complex functions. Consequently, the brain operates dynamically across three levels based on situational demands: 1) sub-critical dynamics characterized by high coordination and low variability, 2) supra-critical dynamics marked by low coordination and high variability, and 3) critical dynamics that exhibit both high coordination and high variability.

Transitions between these critical states, particularly near the critical points, necessitate significant fluctuations in non-linear network activity, which is highly sensitive to minute quantum-level fluctuations (London et al. 2010). Such quantum-level perturbations can initiate avalanches, pushing them beyond critical thresholds and consequently altering the state of consciousness. It is theorized that the brain delicately balances between order and chaos (Aaronson 2016). Thus, it is plausible that the amplification of quantum fluctuations can guide brain activity toward a critical point of neuronal dynamics. This mechanism enables quantum dynamics to persist within a network of highly interconnected neurons, perpetually poised on the cusp between quantum chaos and quantum

stability. This arrangement suggests that certain quantum events (e.g., quantum tunnelling) may be influenced by others (e.g., extracellular electric waves), potentially leading to substantial alterations in the synchronization of neuronal firing and, consequently, a distinct pattern of functional output within neuronal networks. These alterations can profoundly impact cognition, behaviour, consciousness, or unconsciousness (Anastassiou & Koch 2015).

Conclusion

Comprehending the influence of quantum physics at the level of subatomic particles on brain function has presented significant challenges in recent decades. Multiple research groups have suggested that the human brain, like all matter in the universe, adheres to the principles of quantum physics. Numerous studies have indicated that certain aspects of decision-making behaviour are more effectively explained by a quantum probability framework than by classical probability theories (Wang et al. 2014). Quantum particles within atoms, such as electrons, have been shown to generate electrical waves that traverse the nervous system. The ultimate output of this intricate, non-linear system of interconnected neuronal networks manifests in a broad range of human cognitive functions, encompassing human behaviour and the state of consciousness. Notably, the functionality of this system is exquisitely sensitive to minute fluctuations in quantum particle activity, which subsequently influence neuronal activity. While recent insights have been offered regarding the involvement of various aspects of quantum physics (e.g., quantum tunnelling and quantum enlargement) in the generation and alteration of consciousness levels, further direct experimental evidence is required to substantiate the quantum brain hypothesis.

However, it is essential to note that the quantum cognition theory and its findings do not necessarily imply that the brain employs quantum events to implement quantum

cognition (Busemeyer, Fakhari & Kvam 2017). The question of whether quantum physics plays a role in the emergence of cognition from neural activity remains an open and intriguing inquiry.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.